

Analytical characterisation of soil samples polluted by industrial effluents for exchangeable cations

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The prominent exchangeable cations Ca-Mg and Na-K have been determined in soils collected near the vicinity of textile industries for the purpose of pollution monitoring using classical methodology of EDTA complexation and flame photometry.

Jodhpur is situated in western part of Indian subcontinent which is covered mainly by desert sands, but some exposure of rock formation has provided an exclusively range of mineral and building materials such as limestone and marble. It has led to the set-up of various type of industries mainly lime, cement, metal, chemical and textile. The fall-out of their processes percolates through the porous soil which acts as an adsorbent retaining a large part of colloidal and soluble ions causing chronic pollution. It is done by the cation exchange capacity of soil where Ca-Mg and Na-K are prominent ions. Although adsorption and cation exchange in soils are of great practical significance by which micronutrients are made available to plants in accordance with hydrogen ion activity and conductivity of soil¹. The flow of waste waters containing hazardous substances and excessive use of fertilizers to enhance crop yield has deepened the problem of soil contamination. The presence of high level of exchangeable cations in soil makes it ineffective in terms of nutrient retention and fertility². For example, higher levels of sodium is associated with salt water pollution which kills plants. The ratio of Na to total cation is important in agriculture and consequently in human pathology. Soil permeability has been harmed by a higher sodium ratio³.

The determination of calcium and magnesium in soils has been studied extensively. The classical gravimetric methods based on the precipitation of calcium oxalate and magnesium ammonium phosphate have largely been replaced by faster and equally accurate methods. Volumetric such as calcium by permanganate and magnesium with 8-hydroxy quinoline were the first major changes. Later on Schwarzenbach and coworkers⁴ reported a procedure depending upon the property of salts of ethylene-diamine tetracetic acid to form complexes with Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions. The simplicity and rapidity of the EDTA titration proce-

dure make it the method of choice for general use, however, colorimetry⁵, spectrophotometry⁶ and AAS⁷ for the determination of calcium and magnesium are also described. Flame photometry has largely been reported for the estimation of potassium and sodium in soils^{8,9}. Gommy *et al.*¹⁰ have described extraction and determination of exchangeable cations using magnesium nitrate solution. The quantitation of potassium by a quartz crystal microbalance has been given by Teresa *et al.*¹¹.

In the present communication we report the results of determination of Na-K and Ca-Mg in polluted soil samples using complexometric and flame photometric methods. The work is a part of pollution studies on industrial waste waters of Jodhpur area. The studies assume paramount importance because there is very limited sources of water and crop production, and thus the contamination of soil as well as underground water may degradate the fertility of soil. In this process, the determination of metallic contaminants such as mercury¹², arsenic¹³, chromium¹⁴, lead and cadmium¹⁵, has already been reported.

Results and discussion

Test solutions were prepared by removing the organic matter present in soil extract to ensure complete solubilization of exchangeable cations. 25 ml aliquot was evaporated to dryness followed by a treatment with aqua regia. Residue was dissolved in deionised water and made up to the requisite volume¹⁶.

Sequential determination of Ca and Mg :

EDTA titrimetric method enables the determination of calcium and magnesium. Therefore these have been determined as Ca individually and Ca-Mg (total) stepwise so as to evaluate the concentration of Mg, as follows :

Ca determination : A pretreated soil sample was titrated with EDTA using murexide at pH \approx 12 to estimate concen-

tration of calcium.

Ca-Mg (total) determination : 10 ml aliquot of soil sample was taken with 1 ml of $\text{NH}_3\text{-NH}_4\text{Cl}$ buffer to make pH ≈ 10 which was titrated with EDTA using erichrome black T indicator, so as to obtain the total calcium and magnesium content in sample.

Mg determination : The concentration of magnesium in sample was obtained based on the difference between Ca-Mg (total) and Ca concentrations.

Determination of K and Na : The concentration of potassium and sodium in soils was determined by flame photometric method where sample was sprayed into a gas flame for carrying the excitation. The calibration curves were drawn from a series of standards of potassium and sodium. 10 ml aliquot of sample was analysed at 589 nm and 768 nm for Na and K, respectively.

Results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of Ca, Mg, K and Na in soils

Sl. no.	Exchangeable cation	N	Concn. (ppm)			S.D. (\pm)	C.V. (%)
			Min	Max.	Ave.		
1.	Ca^{2+}	4	46.0	280.0	146.50	1.05	0.72
2.	Mg^{2+}	4	6.2	22.6	15.95	0.54	3.38
3.	Na^+	3	30.0	130.0	82.16	0.51	1.21
4.	K^+	3	1.5	35.0	17.50	0.56	3.20

N = No. of determinations.

Conclusion :

The higher levels of exchangeable cations particularly sodium and its salts may cause soil salinization. It is an important aspect in present studies because in arid climate of Rajasthan leaching of salts is not so complete as in humid regions. In addition there is a high evaporation rate which tend to concentrate more salts in soil. This raises the risk of affecting the fertility of soil inhibiting plant growth and ultimately limitations in farming.

Experimental

Instrumentation : A Systronics Mediflame 127 was used for flame emission spectroscopic experiments where gas and air are introduced at a controlled rate into a mixing chamber. The air draws in the liquid through the capillary and atomises it into a fine spray. The mixture of gas, air and atomized liquid is ignited at the burner top, and the characteristic emission is noted.

Sample collection : Soil samples were collected from

different sites of Marudhar and Basni industrial areas of Jodhpur, having industries of dye production, non-ferrous metal, smelting minerals, chemicals etc. To ensure a representative sample of a site, six sub samples were collected within a ten meter radius and mixed thoroughly. These were taken in polyethylene bags using a stainless steel tube sampler of 5 cm diameter to enable soil removal upto a depth of atleast 5 cm. A minimum mass of 50 g was collected from each sampling point.

Analytically grade chemicals were used. All stock solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Standards of sodium and potassium were prepared from NaCl and KCl, respectively.

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